

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

CREATORS OF BROWN ROT ON TREES USED IN FORESTS AND PARKS OF THE CENTRAL CITIES OF AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The main goal of my work is to study the taxonomic composition, morphological features and biological development of tree microbiota (native and introduction), used in landscaping the largest cities of Azerbaijan, Baku and Ganja, to study the patterns of formation of the pathocomplex in them. It has been established that the fungi involved in the formation of microbiota of trees and shrubs used in horticulture in Baku and Ganja have a high pathogenicity and, to some extent, fungi comprise 72.6% of the total number of fungies. It was shown that among the trees used in landscaping, pine, cypress, medlar, eastern maple and oak are characterized as more stable, ordinary poplar and white tut as unstable species.

Keywords: tree, fungies, mycobiota, pathogen types, bushes.

The main goal of my work is to study the taxonomic composition, morphological features and biological development of the microbiota of trees (native and introduced) used in the landscaping of the largest cities of Azerbaijan Baku and Ganja, to study the patterns of formation of the pathocomplex in them. It has been established that the fungi involved in the formation of the microbiota of trees and shrubs used in horticulture in Baku and Ganja are highly pathogenic and, to some extent, fungi account for 72.6% of the total number of fungi. Among the trees used in landscaping, pine, cypress, medlar, oriental maple and oak have been shown to be more resistant, common poplar and white tutu as unstable species.

Our study was investigated on the mycobiota of trees and shrubs used in landscaping in Baku and Ganja, on their ecological and trophic relationships, on the distribution of fungi on individual plants, as well as on the biological resistance of trees and shrubs. It was found that the manifestations of pathogenic species in the mycobiota of trees and bushes used in the cities we mentioned are more likely to be associated with diseases such as brown and white rot.

Prior to our study, trees and shrubs used in the landscaping of Baku and Ganja, the largest cities of Azerbaijan, were not the subject of systematic micro-research. It should be added that Azerbaijan is generally considered to be one of the less forested countries [1], so landscaping is an important issue in Azerbaijan.

Decay is the decomposition and facilitation of plant tissues created by fungi and bacteria. Rot and mold, as well as root and stem rot, were found in fruits and seeds. Root rot prevents the roots from absorbing water and nutrients from the soil and causes the trees to dry out [2]. Drying branches - the death of individual branches and the entire crown, hill and crown. The disease can be caused by branch infection, root rot and lack of moisture in the soil. Fungal diseases are more common. They do more damage than other parasites, microorganisms and flower parasites. Diseases are mainly related to basidiomycetes and imperfect fungi, macro- and micromycetes

Thus, from the above data, it is clear that fungi can cause various diseases, and their prevalence, manifestation and degree of damage are widely characterized. The absence of differentiated fungi makes it impossible to accurately identify these deficiencies. However, extensive research is currently underway in this area, and hundreds of symptoms of fungal diseases have been identified and countermeasures developed.

As a result of the foregoing, landscaping is a permanent and necessary element of modern urban life, and its safety in many aspects, including mycology, is one of the urgent tasks of modern biology, including mycology. Research in this area is a reality dictated by the modern era.

Baku is also rich in minerals such as oil and gas, and for the second century they have been intensively processed from its territory. The chemical industry is also one of the most developed and expanding industries in the city of Baku. Mineral waters and many mud volcanoes are also typical for the nature of Baku. Baku and Ganja are typical for large cities and have a constant anthropogenic impact on the environment, so special attention should be paid to its landscaping. Currently, according to available information, hundreds of trees, shrubs and herbs are used in the landscaping of Baku, including both native and non-native species of flora. It should be noted that one of the places where people spend the whole day are parks where there is landscaping. These plants are also one of the habitats of fungi, and in terms of ecotrophic interactions between these fungi, there are a sufficient number of species that have certain pathogens. Fungi that meet these characteristics are not only a source of threat to plants, microorganisms, animals, but also to humans. Samples taken from the trees for examination were either fungal, i.e. micromycetes were either washed or transferred to a nutrient medium, or processes were carried out to obtain a pure culture by transferring this part to a nutrient medium. Culture media were used for purified cultured fungi on test plants using malt juice agar (ACC), rice agar (RA), starch (AA) and potato (AA), Capek and Chapek-Dox agar media. Preparation, sterilization of the medium and filling into Petri flasks were carried out according to known methods [3,4].

1. *Abortipus borealis*- Mushrooms, called the northern bubble, were found only twice during the research, that is, they are considered random species of the general microbiota of trees and shrubs used in landscaping in Baku and Ganja. Fungi are phytopathogens and cause rot in the host plant, which also has a color that causes destructive rot.

2. *Armillaria mellea*- Although it belongs to the category of edible mushrooms, it is biotrophic and has an enzyme system capable of catalyzing the breakdown of all the major polymers present in wood. It is one of the most common mushrooms in Azerbaijan, and the most common species are broad-leaved plants.

3. *Botrytis cinerea*- Research on this fungus that causes gray rot has been found in the grapevine. Earlier, this fungus was also found in mycological studies in

Azerbaijan. It is characterized by broad substrate specificity.

4. *Fomes fomentarius* - Known as the true mushroom, this fungus is rarely found on trees used for urban landscaping and has been found in common poplar during research (picture 2). However, this fungus belongs to the true biotrophs due to the most common and ecotrophic features of the xylomycobiota, characteristic of the Azerbaijani forests.

5. *Fomitopsis rosea*- This fungus, which is a natural rotting creature under natural conditions, has been found to live in chestnut oak. The mushroom, which has its own characteristics, is also one of the mushrooms that has been identified in research in this field. (picture 1).

Pic.1 *Fomitopsis rosea* pic.2 *Fomes fomentarius*

The experiments were carried out to obtain information about pathogenic fungal diseases associated with the formation of the microbiota of trees, to study their prevalence and development cycles of some pathogens used in landscaping in Baku and Ganja. The main reason for these studies is that the degree of damage to certain diseases caused by fungi is determined by the biological status of the creator and the plant, their interaction under certain environmental conditions, the natural climate, flora and fauna of their territory. As a result, fungi that spread in different climates can cause various diseases. The focus of infection and structures begin to appear on infected trees.

Mass infection of forest trees from dangerous diseases and at the same time the creation of large areas for drying is called epitotia. Three factors influence the process of ephitotia: high infection rate, disease resistance and favorable weather, among others. Clarification of these issues is also important for the mycological evaluation of trees and shrubs in any ecosystem. Therefore, studies have been carried out to identify diseases caused by fungi and their creators. From the results, it became clear that the most common disease is rot and spotting in various types of mushrooms.

Fungal diseases observed in trees involved in greening and their prevalence (%)

N	Name of the disease	The causative agent of the disease	Observable tree	Propagation rate
1	Brown stem rot	<i>I.Hispidus</i>	Japanese safora white tut white locust	12,6-56,7
2	Brown stem rot	<i>F.Pinicola</i>	common poplar	7,8-12,8
3	Brown root rot	<i>F.Pini</i>	southern willow spruce	2,1-4,3

One noteworthy item in the table is that it has a relatively high incidence caused by anamorphic fungal populations. The telemorphic form of one or another pathogen occurs either after the death of the plant or its fungus, or the wintering of the plant.

Thus, studies have shown that trees and shrubs used in greenery in Baku and Ganja are considered one of the most common habitats for fungi, among which there are new microbiota species characteristic of Azerbaijani nature and the vast majority of fungi. This feature is associated with diseases such as brown and white rot of the bark, the prevalence of which is 0.7-12.8%. All this suggests that the problem of mycobiota safety of trees and shrubs used in landscaping is always in the spotlight, and that the current monitoring system is being improved.

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